

monsoon period. TNAU finally selected one such culture, TNAU 13493, and released it for cultivation in 1977 as Co 40 Rajarajan. This variety grows to 110 cm and matures in 165 to 170 days. Its grain is short and bold and the length:width ratio is 2.23. The vegetative period extends from 110 to 115 days.

Some significant characteristics of Rajarajan are 1) medium-tall stature with lodging resistance, 2) photoperiod sensitivity, 3) high photosynthetic ability even in cloudy monsoon weather,

4) resistance to *Pyricularia*, 5) high field tolerance for bacterial blight, 6) nitrogen utilization at moderate levels (80–120kg/ha), and 7) high yielding ability (from 6 to 7.5 t/ha vs 3 to 3.5 t/ha for the existing tall indica varieties) (see table).

Seedlings of Rajarajan can be planted after 50 to 60 days in the nursery beds so that its 110- to 115-day field duration is in the management limit of small farmers with available rainfall and a little stored water left in seasonal ponds during

postmonsoonal dry periods.

The yields of Rajarajan in research stations, adaptation trials in farmers' fields, and demonstration plots from 1974 to 1977 are given in the table. Other advantages are its yield stability across seasons and locations, and its medium-tall stature that makes it a source of rice straw, a stable feed for cattle in this region. Rajarajan is well received by the local farmers.

Fifteen participants in 1978 GEU training program

Fifteen participants from Bangladesh, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and Thailand attended the 1978 Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) training program at IRRI from February 15 to June 16 (see photo). The course includes both instruction and practical experience in the basic skills essential to the operation of successful rice improvement programs, emphasizing and demonstrating the importance of multidisciplinary cooperation.

The GEU training program is basically skills oriented. Participants enhance their competence in screening to identify desirable rice characters, in combining such characters through selective plant

Participants in the 1978 GEU training program checking their hybridized plants in the IRRI plant breeding greenhouse. From left to right are: S. Ponnuthurai, D. L. Wichremasingha, and G. G. Saparamadu from Sri Lanka; M. Potisurintara, A. Thaotho from Thailand; I. Hadisjaban, A. Subardjo, A. Kartohardjono, Z. A. Simanullang, Sumarno, and A. E. Kosman from Indonesia; and M. B. Alam, Q. A. Haque, Md. A. Hossain, and P. K. S. Ray from Bangladesh.

breeding, and in evaluating the progeny. Candidates for GEU training are carefully selected. Only highly motivated

and active rice scientists of leadership potential with a knack for hard work qualify.

The diffusion of specific semidwarf rices as parents in Asian rice breeding programs over 10 years

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Although researchers have traced the spread of the improved rice varieties onto farmers' fields, little is known about their diffusion as parent varieties into breeding programs. Through analysis of breeding records and in-depth interviews with rice breeders, the International Rice Research Institute studied changes in the rices used as parents in 355 randomly selected crosses made over a 10-year period at 14 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 7 Asian nations: Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Korea, Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. The

research project was partially funded by a grant from The Rockefeller Foundation. The most popular single gene source in the 1965–67 sample of crosses was Taichung Native 1 (TN1), a semidwarf variety developed in Taiwan in 1956. TN1 was used in 22% of the total crosses, IR8 in 20%, and other IRRI lines in 14% (see figure, A).

By 1970, the use of TN1 had dropped sharply: by 1974–75 TN1 was used in only 1% of the crosses. The use of IR8 increased slightly by 1970–71, but dropped to only 3% by 1974–75. The use of IRRI varieties and lines other than IR8 as parents increased to about 44% of the crosses by 1974–75; the use of semidwarfs introduced from other countries also increased slightly.

But the strongest trend was the growing use of *locally developed*

A. Use of semidwarf parents in the rice breeding programs of 7 Asian nations over a 10-year period. Eight hundred and nineteen parents used in 355 randomly selected crosses at 14 agricultural experiment stations and universities.

B. Use of semidwarf parents in Indian rice breeding programs over a 10-year period. Three hundred parents used in 140 randomly selected crosses at 7 agricultural experiment stations and universities, India.

C. Use of semidwarf parents in rice breeding programs of 6 Asian nations (excluding India) over a 10-year period. Five hundred and nineteen parents used in 215 randomly selected crosses at 7 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 6 Asian nations, 1965-75.

semidwarfs – from almost zero to use in almost half of the crosses in 10 years. Most of such semidwarfs were progeny of earlier crosses with TN1 or IR8.

Because more than a third of the crosses analyzed were made at seven research centers in India, the data were analyzed to determine if Indian rice

breeders differed from fellow rice breeders in the six other nations in the adoption of genetic materials.

By 1974–75, 75% of the crosses made in the Indian sample involved a locally developed semidwarf; 21% involved an IRRI parent other than IR8; and 7%, a semidwarf introduced from another

country (figure, B). In the six other countries, IRRI was the major source of semidwarf parents (figure, C). But the same strong trend toward the use of locally developed semidwarfs was found.

The 111 times that a semidwarf variety was used as a parent in 1974–75 involved 83 separate varieties or breeding lines.

Ancestry of locally developed semidwarf rices used as parents in Asian rice breeding programs in 1974–75

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In a study of the diffusion of genetic materials among rice breeding programs in different countries of Asia, almost half of the 377 randomly selected crosses made in 1974–75 at 14 agricultural experiment stations in 7 Asian nations involved the use of at least one *locally developed* parent. The sources of the semidwarf gene were determined by analyzing the ancestry of the local semidwarfs. Genes were traced back two or three generations.

Seventy-six percent of the local semidwarf parents were progeny of IR8 or other IRRI varieties and lines (see figure, A). For example, the variety K35, used as a parent in India, is a progeny of the cross IR8/HR19; RD1, used in Thailand, is from Leuang Tawng/IR8.

Twenty-four percent of the local

semidwarfs such as Sona (TN1/GEB 24) and Jaya (TN1/T141) were progeny of TN1. Twenty-five percent of the rices had at least two different semidwarf parents; for example Tong-il, often used in Korean crosses, is from the cross IR8//Yukara/TN1.

But a fourth of the local semidwarf parents were themselves progenies of local semidwarfs that had been developed earlier. The genetic composition of those second-generation ancestors was determined next. Eighty percent were found to be progeny of TN1 (figure, B), Thirty-three percent had both TN1 and IR8 in their ancestry. For example, Pusa 33, used in three crosses, is a progeny of a cross of Ratna (TKM 6/IR8) with Improved Sabarmati (TN1*3/Basmati 370).

Because TN1, IR8, and most other semidwarfs have Dee-geo-woo-gen (DGWG) as a common ancestor, the DGWG gene may be assumed to be in about 80% of the crosses analyzed for 1974–75.

A. Source of semidwarf gene in 59 locally developed semidwarf rices used as parents in 1974–75 crosses. B. Source of semidwarf gene in the ancestors of local semidwarfs that were used as parents in 1974–75 crosses.